

Developing plain language summaries for single technology appraisals (protocol)

EAG methodology topic commissioned by the NIHR Evidence Synthesis Programme on behalf of the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence

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1 Plain Language Summary

In the UK, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) advises on drugs and technologies for the NHS in England and Wales. NICE looks at how well a new treatment works and whether it is good value for money through its Technology Appraisal (TA) Programme. The Single Technology Appraisal (STA) is the most common NICE appraisal process. In a STA, the company that makes the new treatment gives evidence about how well it works and its cost in a document called the company submission (CS).

Independent academic groups, called External Assessment Groups (EAGs), review these company submissions. They check the evidence to make sure it is right and can be trusted. NICE's appraisal process also involves clinical experts, patients and the public.

Currently, EAG reports for STAs do not include plain language summaries (PLSs). PLSs are easy-to-read summaries of research. They help non-technical readers understand the methods and findings. The lack of PLSs makes it harder for lay committee members, public contributors, and experts by lived experience to access the information.

We aim to create a PLS template and guidance to be used in EAG reports. We will start by reviewing key issues of existing STAs. Following this, we will run focus groups with intended readers of the PLS. We will explore what information they value most in a PLS and how it should best be presented. Based on this input, we will draft a PLS template, guidance, and a worked example. We will then run first-stage user testing to measure users understanding of the PLS examples. We will use their feedback to refine the template and guidance. Patient representatives will be involved in the core research team, sharing their experiences and views throughout the project.

2 Background

Too often the patients and carers who live with a health condition, or who are intended to benefit from the outputs of research and policy, are not involved in the processes that shape them. A patient-centred approach empowers patients to actively participate in and make decisions about their own healthcare (1). Health research agencies recognise the value of such involvement and increasingly mandate that patients and members of the public are embedded in the research process. Similarly, Health Technology Assessment bodies involve the patient and public perspective in decision-making about reimbursement for individual medicines and interventions (2). Research findings are often disseminated through articles in peer-reviewed journals and conference presentations. However, these reports are typically jargon-laden (3) and data-intensive; formats that are difficult for a lay audience to understand (4). Gainey et al report that although journals offer author instructions, the PLSs published in health journals typically lack concordance with that guidance (5).

Plain language summaries (PLSs) are an important topic for development. In health research, a PLS is a stand-alone summary of a piece of research that helps non-technical readers to understand the methods and findings. PLSs are often the first point of entry for readers of health research (6).

In the UK, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) provides advice on medicines and treatments for the NHS in England and Wales. NICE assesses the clinical and cost-effectiveness of new interventions through its Technology Appraisal (TA) Programme. The Single Technology Appraisal (STA) is the most common NICE appraisal process. NICE introduced STAs in 2005. STAs specifically appraise new technology for a single indication, with one or more standard treatment comparators. This process allows NICE to deliver more timely guidance to the NHS. The manufacturer of the new medicine submits evidence to NICE, in the form of a company submission (CS). Companies provide clinical- and cost-effectiveness evidence on the technology being evaluated.

External Assessment Groups (EAGs) (also known as Technology Assessment Groups (TAGs)) are independent academic centres commissioned by NICE and the NIHR to review and critique CSs. Within an STA, the EAG produces an external assessment report for the appraisal committee. The external assessment report contains an overview of the EAGs critique, including the identification of methodological strengths and weaknesses in the submitted evidence. The EAG reports these as “key issues” that covers both clinical and cost-effectiveness evidence.

Companies submit economic models that provide a structured framework for estimating costs and health outcomes based on evidence from multiple sources (7). These are central to decision-making deliberations by NICE committees. The robustness of these models depends on factors such as whether the model structure reflects the disease pathway, the relevance and accuracy of the supporting clinical data, and the absence of errors (8). To ensure models are appropriately informed, clinical effectiveness analyses aim to provide precise and unbiased estimates of treatment effects. This requires careful consideration of how representative the study populations are to routine practice in the NHS, the appropriateness of comparators and outcomes, heterogeneity between studies, and the validity and quality of included evidence. By critically evaluating these components, EAGs ensure that both the clinical and economic evidence underpinning the appraisal is rigorous and reliable.

The HTA process involves input from various groups, including patients and the public (9). NICE TA committees invite clinical experts and experts by lived experience to participate in the meetings. Both groups of experts have full access to committee papers but neither of these groups has voting rights. TA committees have lay members whose role is to present and include the patient, carer, and public perspective into the deliberation and decision making. Lay members have full voting rights and decision-making powers.

Companies provide a Summary of Information for Patients (SIP) as part of their evidence submission, a requirement introduced relatively recently in 2021 (10). However, currently PLSs are not included in EAG reports of STAs, which limits their accessibility to lay committee members, invited experts by lived experience, and the public. A PLS of the EAG report would enable lay committee members, invited experts, and members of the public to access and better understand the key issues.

We aim to develop a PLS template for inclusion in EAG reports, and accompanying guidance for EAG members who produce STA reports to help them produce the PLS.

Although our work focuses on STAs, the resulting guidance may also be applicable to other NICE processes, such as Highly Specialised Technology (HST) evaluations and cost-comparison assessments—any process in which EAGs are responsible for synthesising company-submitted evidence into reports. Beyond NICE, the guidance has the potential to provide wider value to the scientific community by offering a structured, patient-informed approach to producing clear and accessible summaries of complex evidence.

3 Methods

We will follow the following stages to develop the PLS template and accompanying guidance for inclusion in EAG reports:

- (1) Review key issues in a sample of existing STAs
- (2) Conduct focus groups with lay committee members, invited experts, and the public
- (3) Develop a template and guidance for PLS EAG reports of STA based on the findings from the first two stages
- (4) Conduct one-on-one user testing to gain feedback on the proposed template
- (5) Iteratively refine and finalise template and guidance based on user testing

3.1 Stage 1: Review of key issues in existing STAs

We will conduct a review to identify key issues across a random sample of EAG STA reports published since 2023. This will help inform guidance on how to write a plain language summary for the EAG report for an STA.

3.1.1 Methods

3.1.1.1 Data sources

We will identify all STAs published since 1 January 2023 from the NICE website (<https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/published?ndt=Guidance&ngt=Technology+appraisal+guidance>). We chose this date because it is approximately one year after the NICE methods guide was updated in January 2022, meaning STAs published from 2023 are likely to have been developed in accordance with the revised guidance.

We will download the full list of appraisals into an excel spreadsheet. We will use a random number generator in excel to allocate a random number to each STA. We will then sort on random number from low to high. We will work through the committee papers for these STAs, extracting information as outlined below until we achieve data saturation. This will be when we identify no new themes.

3.1.1.2 Data extraction

NICE publishes committee papers for each appraisal on their website. We will extract data from the EAG report, found within the committee papers for search selected STA. We will not consider subsequent documents such as the factual accuracy check, EAG addendums, or results from additional analysis conducted after the original report was submitted.

We will extract data on the following characteristics for each STA:

- Condition

- Intervention
- Company that produces the drug
- Company that prepared the company submission (if different)
- Publication date
- EAG that produced the report

We will extract all “key issues” raised in the report from the executive summary both for the clinical- and cost-effectiveness sections of the report. Key issues are required to be reported in the executive summary and are labelled as such, with Table 1 usually providing an overview of the key issues that have been identified. We will categorise key issues as relating to the following components of the company submission:

- Decision problem
- Evidence review - excluding statistical synthesis
- Evidence review - statistical synthesis
- Primary studies
- Economic model inputs
- Economic model assumptions

3.1.1.3 *Synthesis*

We will synthesise the extracted data using a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches. First, we will conduct a thematic synthesis of the key issues within each category. This will involve identifying recurring patterns and sub-themes by letting them naturally emerge from the reports and developing a narrative summary of these themes. For example, within economic model assumptions these may be: survival extrapolation, choice of comparators, or handling of adverse events. Secondly, we will quantify the number of key issues falling within each predefined category (decision problem, evidence review, economic model inputs, and economic model assumptions) and examine trends in their distribution across different characteristics of the STAs, including condition, intervention, EAG, and year of publication.

3.2 Stage 2: Focus groups

The findings from stage 1 will inform stage 2. For this we will hold two focus groups to explore how different users use PLS, what information they would like to find in a PLS, and how we can best communicate some of the more complex issues associated with STAs. This includes key issues with the clinical and cost effectiveness evidence, methodological weaknesses in the company submission and any additional work carried out by the EAG. We will explore participants views on some initial example PLS for EAG reports of STAs completed by Bristol TAG.

3.2.1 Participant selection

We aim to recruit a maximum of 16 participants across two focus groups. We will conduct one group involving invited experts by clinical expertise. We will conduct another group involving lay TA committee members, invited experts by lived experience, and members of the public. We will send out email invites to potential participants of the focus groups. We

will intentionally recruit for a diversity of perspectives and experience. We will recruit participants through purposive sampling using established contacts. Lay TA committee members, invited experts by clinical and lived experience, and members of the public will be identified and contacted via colleagues and associates at NICE or from the Bristol TAG's established patient database in order to recruit members of the public. We will adopt an iterative approach throughout and sampling strategies will be amended if the study team considers there to be an inadequate diversification of views.

3.2.2 Invitation and consent

We will email to invite people to attend a 1.5-hour long online focus group via Microsoft Teams. We will provide participants with an information sheet that will:

- outline the study aims
- give a brief overview of the procedure
- detail the participant information we will collect

We will ask participants to complete a consent form, which they will be asked to sign, and to initial specific statements to indicate that they agree to each of these statements on the consent form. Participants will be informed of their right to withdraw and assured of confidentiality and anonymity of data. The requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) will be complied with at all times and only personal data necessary for the purposes of the research will be collected.

3.2.3 Materials and data extraction and analysis

We will build on the findings from Stage 1 and produce a structured topic guide for the focus group. This will be informed by the key issues identified in the review of existing STAs and will incorporate specifically developed PLS examples to support discussion.

Examples of plain language summaries (PLSs) and plain language adaptations of key issues will be purposefully developed and selected to reflect a range of content, formats, and complexity. Draft PLS materials will be produced by the research team using plain language principles.

During the focus groups, discussion will aim to

- Explore participant experience and the perceived need for a PLS, including reviewing selected examples that illustrate different approaches to presenting information
- Refine and develop the PLS template and guidance, including considerations around structure, level of detail, terminology and appropriate length
- Examine and discuss selected examples, including draft PLSs of STAs developed for the focus groups and plain language examples of the top key issues identified in Stage 1.

We will audio-record and transcribe the focus group meeting using Microsoft Teams. Anonymised transcripts will be checked for accuracy and imported into QSR NVIVO qualitative data analysis software. We will conduct a thematic analysis, utilising a data-driven inductive approach. We will scrutinise the data to identify and analyse patterns and themes across the dataset using constant comparison techniques.

All data will be stored securely on University of Bristol SharePoint. The data will only be accessible by the researchers working on this project and will be deleted after the project has ended and the data are no longer required.

3.3 Stage 3: Development of PLS template

We will collate insights from the review and focus group discussion to draft a PLS template and accompanying guidance for EAG report authors. We anticipate that this guidance will offer directions on what to include, how to explain technical terms specific to STAs based on findings from the review of key issues, and what information should go into particular sections. It will also contain some example phrases and options to communicate the evidence.

3.4 Stage 4: One-on-one user testing

Following the development of the draft template and guidance, we will conduct one-on-one user testing. We will ask participants for their views and understanding of different PLS examples for the same EAG report.

3.4.1 Participant selection

We aim to recruit 4 participants from the focus groups to take part in the user testing. We will contact all participants that took part in the focus group discussion and, from the positive responses, we will select four members with an equal representation of NICE lay committee members and lay members of the public. We recognise that, given the small and likely homogenous sample, this testing represents an initial step rather than a definitive evaluation. Nevertheless, it will provide valuable insights to inform refinement of the template and guidance.

3.4.2 Invitation and consent

We will email the participants to invite them to attend a 60-90 minutes long one-to-one user testing session via Microsoft Teams. We will provide participants with an information sheet that will:

- outline the study aims
- give a brief overview of the procedure
- details the participant information we will collect

We will ask participants to read and consider the consent form. If they agree to participate, we will ask them to sign, and to initial specific statements to indicate that they agree to each statement on the consent form. We will inform participants that they have the right to withdraw from the study at any time and assure them of confidentiality and anonymity of their data. We will comply with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) at all times and only collect personal data that is necessary for the purposes of the research.

3.4.3 Materials and data extraction and analysis

We will produce a structured topic guide for the first-stage user testing. The user testing sessions will be audio-recorded using encrypted devices and transcribed using Microsoft

Teams. Anonymised transcripts will be checked for accuracy and imported into QSR NVIVO qualitative data analysis software. Thematic analysis, utilising a data-driven inductive approach, will be used to scrutinise the data to identify and analyse patterns and themes across the dataset using constant comparison techniques.

Data will be collected and stored securely on University of Bristol SharePoint. The data will only be accessible by the researchers working on this project. We will delete the data after the project has ended and the data are no longer required.

3.5 Stage 5: Finalise PLS template

The final stage of the project will involve finalising the PLS structure and its accompanying guidance, incorporating feedback gathered from the user testing.

4 Output

Our main output for this project will be guidance for EAG report authors on how to write a PLS for technology appraisals, with accompanying examples. We will share this document with other EAGs. We will publish our research findings in peer-reviewed journals. We will present our findings to relevant audiences such as the HTAi (Health Technology Assessment International) special interest groups.

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6 Ethics

This project received ethical approval from the Faculty of Health Sciences Research Ethics Committee on 02/05/2025.

7 Declaration of interests

None

8 References

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